

ADMINISTRATIVE COSTS IN THE US HEALTHCARE SYSTEM: IS SIMPLIFICATION AND TECHNOLOGY A SOLUTION TO EFFICIENCY AND GROWING HEALTHCARE COSTS?

Faisal Iqbal

International Labour Organisation, Islamabad, Pakistan

sinjhoro@hotmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

With the conclusion of elections in the United State of America, the Government is aiming to reduce the Government's expenditure by USD 2 Trillion and increase efficiency by dismantling bureaucracies. It is, therefore, timely to review as if the latest research supports this. This paper assesses the proclaimed cost cutting and inefficiency in the healthcare administration of the United States by focusing only on billing practices, paperwork, claims processing, and emergency preparedness. It examines as if the digital technologies like artificial intelligence, telemedicine, and electronic health records can optimize these processes, cut costs, and improve efficiency. The study draws on latest literature, revealing the potential for cost cutting of up to \$265 billion per annum by simplifying administrative tasks. Further, it also examines the impacts of policy reforms such as No Surprises Act and Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services Price Transparency Rule. The findings show that embracing digital tools and creating standardized systems could greatly reduce the costs and enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the U.S. healthcare system.

INTRODUCTION

The US healthcare system is laden with estimated one trillion-dollar administrative cost out of total four trillion dollars healthcare expenditure annually, making it the highest spender globally. There are around six million administrative staff in the US healthcare system, making the number twice as those of nurses and physicians (Sahini et al., 2021). Further, the waste in the US healthcare system amounts to 265 billion US dollars annually because of its administrative inefficiencies, which include redundant billing processes, excessive paperwork, and inefficient claims processes (McKinsey & Company, 2023). The lack of standardized coding system in billing practices and prolonged time of

claims processing are the major contributors to rising costs. For example, it is estimated that a simple claim process can take four weeks and cost around 40 dollars per transaction (Sahni et al., 2023). Nevertheless, recent study reveals that by integrating digital solutions such as electronic health records (EHRs) and telemedicine, the US healthcare system could save around 90 billion dollars per annum (Health Affairs, 2024). The objective of this paper is to answer the significant question: Will streamlining administrative procedures through digital solutions and key policy reforms cut costs and inefficiencies, while also enhancing the overall performance? By evaluating the recent research and technological

advancements, this paper examines how digitization and efficient processes can drive significant cost cutting and expand healthcare delivery.

Literature Review

Recent research suggest that several scholars have focused on ways and means to address the challenge of inefficiency in the US healthcare administration. This section reviews these studies to analyse the context on simplification of billing practices, reduction of paperwork and introduction of digital solutions, standardization of the claims processes, and improving emergency preparedness. The studies reviewed in this section elaborate on the potential for cost cutting, improved efficiency, and better healthcare giver and patient experiences.

Multiple studies have shown a core focus on simplification of billing practices. For instance, Sahni et al. (2023) focus on inefficiency in “claims processing and prior authorizations,” which almost take four weeks per claim, and incur a cost of around 40 dollars per transaction. On average these billing related costs amount to 200 billion dollars annually. They recommended that by employing the technique of automated claims, the entire processes could be streamlined. Hence, potentially saving up to 60 billion dollars annually. Similarly, Patel and Barton (2022) also criticized the billing and insurance related administrative tasks, urging the need for simplification to avoid accumulating administrative waste. Whereas Cutler (2020) on the other hand suggested introducing regulations, which could develop the “electronic transformation of billing,” thereby, harmonizing data for eminent reporting and applying “prior authorization rules” where needed most.

As far as reduction in the paperwork is concerned, scholars like Sahni et al. (2021), Aljaloud and Razzaq (2023), and Yang et al. (2023) have all stressed on adoption of digital solutions. Sahni et al. (2021) evaluate that by digitizing varied administrative tasks and investing in data management would potentially save 265 billion dollars annually. Aljaloud and Razzaq (2023) through their demonstration show blockchain technology’s potential, which they call “Ethereum-based Healthcare Management System (HMS).” This prototype reduced data fragmentation and improved interoperability with the capabilities of

storing data without being tempered with, hence resulting in securing smart contracts. Similarly, Yang et al. (2023) also demonstrate that large language models (LLMs) significantly cut administrative loads by digitizing tasks such as taking clinical notes and giving briefs of claims data. These scholars have shown that such interventions successfully streamline workflows, reduce errors, and meaningfully and strategically curtail the need for manual intervention. Regulating claims processing is another crucial variable that needs to be digitized to improve efficiency and cost reduction. Chigurupati and Kocher (2021) are of the view that contract complexity hinders claims computerisation, which can be estimated by the fact that 15 percent of electronically submitted claims need manual review. In their recommendations, standardization of contracts and familiarising CMS-led models are significant to enhance efficiency and “provider-payer communication.” Sahni et al. (2023) and Sahni et al. (2021) also argue in favour of “centralized claims clearinghouses and standardized medical policies” to cut redundancy and generate reliability within the healthcare system. Whereas Douven et al. (2022) on the other hand suggest that regularized digital frameworks, where risks are assessed, can improve equity as well as efficiency, more significantly in the area of insurance claims.

The idea of standardization and digital solutions also positively contribute to emergency preparedness framework. It has been shown in the study of Aljaloud and Razzaq (2023) that blockchain technology enhances real-time data accessibility and its security—the most critical aspects during an emergency situation. Similarly, Patil and Shankar (2023) stress that artificial intelligence has now become important factor in operational management, managing the workflow, and analysing the large set of data—consequently improving administrative response within healthcare system, which is extremely beneficial in emergencies. In addition to these scholars, Sahni et al. (2021), digital solutions greatly advance the interoperability aspect, thus aiding speedy coordination during crises.

The review of the literature has shown that recent research on administrative costs and efficiency in healthcare in the US has significantly focused on simplifying billing practices, reducing paperwork

through digital solutions, standardizing claims processing, and emergency preparedness. All of the studies reviewed in this section point to the urgent need of introducing technology driven policy reforms, which could automate health systems through varied digital solutions like AI, blockchain technology, and standardized frameworks. Thus, providing multiple approaches to address the inefficiency in healthcare administration and introduce resilience.

Methodology

The methodology adopted in this paper is qualitative, where secondary data was explored to analyse the administrative costs in the US health care system and answer if simplification of the processes could reduce cost and enhance efficiency. Thereby, the recent academic scholarship, especially post 2020 on the similar grounds was critically reviewed first to understand the context and find relevant themes. The literature revealed themes such as simplification of billing processes, digitization to reduce paperwork, standardizing claims processing, and improvement in emergency preparedness. These themes were further explored in policy and updated recent information to synthesise and evaluate the problem, thereby arriving at the conclusion and suggest pragmatic recommendations.

Findings

This section explains the themes chalked out in literature review below to understand the current dynamics as far as administrative simplification is concerned.

Simplifying Billing Practices

The complex billing procedures in the US healthcare system is among the major causes of administrative inefficiencies, which eventually elevate the overall costs for the healthcare providers as well as the customers. Recent findings reveal that with simplifying the procedures and technological integration, administrative effectiveness can be achieved.

The complexity of the billing processes could be gauged by the fact that as of now, the healthcare providers and insurers in the healthcare system are using diverse coding mechanism and administrative guidelines—therefore lacking uniformity. In this

regard, the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS) is pursuing standardization of “billing codes and processes.” One key aspect of CMS is introducing uniformity in coding, for instance, the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) and Current Procedural Terminology (CPT), which would standardize the processes and reduce the errors, enabling speedy reimbursements (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, n.d.).

More recently, for administrative effectiveness, technological integration is also stressed by the government by introducing the Health Information Technology for Economic and Clinical Health (HITECH) Act. It incentivizes the adoption of electronic health record (EHRs) among healthcare providers. EHR is beneficial as the need for repeated entries of patient data is eliminated with it, which eventually expedite the billing process (HealthIT.gov, n.d.). This is also validated by the research of American Medical Association (AMA, 2020), which concludes that EHR is able to reduce administrative costs significantly. It also eliminates errors in billing, thereby, enabling speedy and exact refunds. Previous research like that of Rand Corporation (2020) already concluded that such steps could reduce the cost by 20 percent.

Furthermore, the CMS Price Transparency Rule (2021) also ask hospitals to provide accurate pricing online, thereby, enabling patients to interpret costs and avoid confusion during billing processes. Additionally, the No Surprises Act (2021) also “limits patient charges to in-network rates for out-of-network emergency services...aiming to reduce financial uncertainty and promote transparency in healthcare billing” (CMS, 2020, 2021). By utilizing these systems, providers can focus on patient care instead of administrative tasks, thus simplifying the billing and making the healthcare system more efficient.

Reducing Paperwork Through Digital Solutions

With paper intensive healthcare system, record keeping, registering patients and issues of claims are yet to be totally shifted to digital spectrum. More importantly, the paperwork is also prone to errors and bad judgements. In a recent study it has been revealed that caregivers spend from around 28 hours to 36 hours on average administrative tasks, most of

which goes to paper-based work (Gupta, 2024). With EHRs such tasks can be digitized saving time and money. After the introduction of HITECH Act of 2009, EHRs adoptions have been substantive. As of now, 96 percent of acute care givers have certified EHRs—whereas the figure for office-based physicians is almost 78 percent (Office of the National Coordinator of Health Information Technology, 2024). Nevertheless, there is still a gap in its adoption in rural areas. It is estimated that across the board EHRs would save approximately 80 billion dollars annually (Kumari & Chander, 2024).

Similarly, telemedicine, is yet another digital solution that came to prominence during the COVID-19 pandemic. Telehealth services does not require physical presence of the patients, thereby reducing paperwork like patient registration forms, verification of insurance, and manual billing. The expansion of this infrastructure would potentially lower administrative costs significantly, especially in cases where follow-up checkups are required or where preventive diagnosis is needed. Thus, in a recent study it is estimated that with the adoption of telemedicine, and average patient will save around 250 dollars of in-person visit to healthcare facilities (Miller, 2024). Moreover, as far as streamlining billing processes is concerned, there is a trend of AI adoption in healthcare facilities across the US. AI is trained to properly evaluate billing data to distinguish patterns, identify errors, and automate coding. Thus, eliminating manual paperwork, and enhancing precision, eventually resulting in less claim denials (McKinsey & Company, 2023).

Standardizing Claims Processing

The deficiency of standardization in claims processing is also one of the major causes of administrative costs in the US healthcare system. As of now, the high costs and prolonged administrative processes are because of healthcare providers submitting claims to diverse insurers—all having diverse rules and protocols—thereby, leading to inefficiencies and delays, as well as disputes between insurance providers and claimants. A recent study of Scheinker et al. (2021) suggest that there is a need of standardization in claims processing by introducing a “single payer model.” They also claim that “single

payer model” has the potential to reduce billing and insurance costs from 33 to 53 percent.

The reliable, fast, and secure electronic data interchange (EDI) is significant in standardization of claims processing. EDI automates data from caregiver to insurer, reducing paperwork and making reimbursements speedy. It is mostly error free as it follows a pattern. The less paperwork means no stored documents, thereby saving administrative costs. It is secure to data breaches and crucial patient information is safe. Overall, it saves 60 percent of traditional administrative costs.

Furthermore, standardization enhances transparency in claims processing, especially where there are uniform reimbursement protocols, which reduces billing surprises and give precise guidelines to patients as well as caregivers. Overall, reducing stress on both parties and enhancing satisfaction. Moreover, there are also efforts to rationalise verification procedures of insurance and prior authorization. Standardization in such instances during electronic transaction reduces delays. This could be also gauged by “Improving Seniors' Timely Access to Care Act,” which aspires to streamline “prior authorization” in Medicare Advantage plans by going digital, and speeding up the process (American Hospital Association, 2021).

Improving Emergency Preparedness

Efficiency in healthcare administration is a significant requirement not only for day-to-day tasks but for catering to emergency situations as well—for instance pandemics, natural calamities, and mass casualties. During the COVID-19, it was revealed how inefficient and slow the response from healthcare givers was, which created panic in the emergency situation. A suitable example here to quote is of insurance claims and their reimbursements, which became hectic functions in absence of digital solutions, thereby, making the expansion of health services in crisis a difficult task. If digital solutions were employed properly, the compensation and payment issues of staff and patients were streamlined, there would not have been mass panics across the US hospitals. Rather, digital solutions would have made patients locations clear, the availability of particular health staff in that location would have been on the dashboard, and

idea of available resources would also have been a click away—making it easier for allocation in emergency (American Hospital Association, 2024, Rand Corporation, 2020).

Discussion

This research findings emphatically support the assertions presented in the section of literature review, i.e., simplifying billing practices, reducing paperwork, and improving claims processing in the US healthcare system. Significant studies like those of Patel and Barton (2022), and Sahni et al. (2023) revealed that the existing billing structure is overly complex, which leads to high cost and inefficiency in the health administration. Sahni et al. (2023) also revealed that only claims processing can take a weeks' time and also cost in billions per annum. The findings of this research also align with this assertion. As it shows that standardization of billing codes and utilising EHRs can exponentially reduce inefficiency, making the reimbursement process speedy, and cut the errors, which is also validated by the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS, n.d.).

It is witnessed in the literature review section that digital solutions are advised by scholars for reducing the paperwork, the findings of this paper further reinforce this idea. For instance, Sahni et al. (2021) and Yang et al. (2023) emphasised the significance of EHRs and telemedicine to eliminate the need of manual work. The findings of this research reveal that EHR implementation has started saving billions and could further save more by eliminating paperwork and associated errors. Further, as Miller (2024) has suggested in the findings, the telemedicine played a key role in COVID-19, and acts as a gamechanger in health systems, as it does not require in-person visits, thereby easing the registration processes, verification of insurance, and eventually saving billions of dollars annually.

Lastly, findings as well as literature review emphasis on standardization of claims processing. Because without it, incidents of delay happen resulting in confusion and higher costs. In this regard, Chigurupati and Kocher (2021) as well as Douven et al. (2022) contended that standardization of contracts and claims processes results in efficiency and reduced gap of communication between insurer and receiver. Furthermore, EDI and the reforms

such as the Improving Seniors' Timely Access to Care Act (American Hospital Association, 2021) also make the process effective as well as reduce delays. Thus, the data of this research suggest that with complete digital integration throughout the healthcare system; efficiency, better care, and cost cutting can be achieved.

Conclusion

To sum up, this research validates the idea of introducing reforms to simplify the administration in the US healthcare system—especially in the areas of billing practices, paperwork elimination, standardizing claims, and response to emergencies. The literature of this research revealed imperative inefficiencies, such as complex billing mechanisms and manual work that also give rise to costs. The results of this research confirm these assertions, suggesting digital solutions such as EHRs, telemedicine, and automated claims processing can overhaul the existing administrative challenges of costs and time.

The implementation of standardized billing codes and upgraded interoperability, as suggested by specialists (Sahni et al., 2023; Patel & Barton, 2022), could rationalise processes and decrease errors, resulting in faster reimbursements. Moreover, the growth of telemedicine has also confirmed the cost cutting by removing the requirement of in-person visits and connected paperwork (Miller, 2024). Also, the reforms such as No Surprises Act and CMS Price Transparency Rule additionally simplify the billing processes improving cost predictability for patients (CMS, 2021).

Despite the positive developments, there are still gaps, especially expansion in the overall digital infrastructure, which becomes more evident in rural areas that hinders full realization of the digital solutions and bringing effectiveness across the healthcare systems in the US. However, by continuous prioritization of digital solutions and standardization, long term administrative efficiency and cost effectiveness along with better patient care can be achieved in the US healthcare system.

Recommendations

As per the results of this research and subsequent analysis, this paper proposes following

recommendations for efficiency and simplification in the US healthcare system,

- **Expand Digital Adoption:** This research recommends provision of incentives for adoption of EHRs and telemedicine, especially in rural and insignificant healthcare systems, which will streamline the process of billing and also reduce paperwork (HealthIT.gov, 2024).
 - **Standardize Billing Practices:** This research recommends across-the-board standardization of billing codes, so that claims processing could be easy for providers as well as insurers (CMS, n.d.; RAND, 2024).
 - **Enhance Policy Reforms:** This research also recommends expansion of No Surprises Act and CMS Price Transparency Rule so that cost predictability can be made patient friendly and disputes are averted (CMS, 2021).
 - **Invest in AI and Automation:** This research recommends investment in AI and automation, so that billing patterns could be identified, codes are automated efficiently, and errors are diminished—consequently refining overall administrative efficiency (McKinsey & Company, 2023).
- The above recommendations significantly cut costs, improve access to healthcare, and streamline the overall patient experience.

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